

IMPROVING READING COMPREHENSION SKILL USING MIND MAPPING TECHNIQUE

Souravi Ata

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education, Jadavpur University, Kolkata

ABSTRACT

Mind maps are visual frameworks such as figures, diagrams, or charts used to present structural knowledge spatially with the intention of empowering comprehension and learning. Mind maps are effective since it clarifies complex concepts into simple, meaningful displays so that learners can develop a holistic understanding of the content to be learnt. Teachers may use mind mapping technique at different stages of instruction i.e. during instruction to prepare students to approach new information and clarify complex ideas and after instruction to assess and reinforce learning and instruction. This article reports on an investigation into the use of mind mapping technique whether it can improve reading comprehension ability and the students' opinions towards the use of mind mapping technique. The research design used in this study was one-group pre-test and post-test design. The study employed quantitative data analyses from pre-and post-tests, a questionnaire. The results suggested that 1) The English reading comprehension post test mean score of students was higher than the pre-test mean score at the 0.05 level of significance; 2) most students were satisfied with their own reading comprehension ability.

Key words: Mind mapping technique, Reading comprehension, Educational process.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is one of the most important skills a student must possess. It is considered the basis of all language skills. Reading is interrelated with the total educational process so that educational success requires successful reading. Experience has taught us that those who fail in school usually have failed first in reading. So, reading is very important in teaching and learning process. It depends on most several processes; the most important of which is reading comprehension. Ortlieb (2013) observed that reading comprehension as the ultimate goal of the reading process. It is a cognitive skill that is connected with the learning process and it directly affects the academic achievement and success in the different academic subjects. So, reading comprehension has become a field of study for different educational and psycho-educational researchers.

Psychologists and educators have different definitions of reading comprehension. Smith (1997) defined reading comprehension as an active process in which learner's interprets the text and modifies it in a manner that suits his ability and his prior knowledge. Grellet (1995) defined it as the ability to comprehend the meaning of the written text and the ability to extract the main ideas efficiently. Lakshmi and Rao (2006) defined reading comprehension as understanding words and sentences in addition to the author's intend meaning regardless of the goal of reading, whether it is for professional knowledge, general information, or fun. Reading comprehension could finally be defined as using the prior knowledge to build the meaning of a text (Lipson & Wixcon, 2009).

Reading comprehension depends on mental perception rather than sensory perception. It begins with the sensory perception of the written word, and it requires concentration, attention, analysis of all elements as an integrated unit, (Al-Tal, 1992). Durkin and Dolores (1995) mentioned that reading comprehension consisted of three main components:

1. ***Understanding vocabulary***: The reader must understand the vocabulary of the text and use his prior knowledge in extracting its meaning and explaining it.
2. ***Understanding the sentence***: The reader must understand the sentence and its relation to the preceding sentence. Of course, the learner's grammatical knowledge has a key role in understanding sentences.
3. ***Understanding the paragraph***: the reader must understand the sentences and their sequence and understand the relationship between them so that he can understand the text.

Reading comprehension includes a number of levels which follow hierarchy. Several researchers classify reading comprehension levels in terms of their number and names. One classification was the one introduced by Burns and Roe (2002) who classified reading comprehension to three levels:

1. ***Reading lines***: It is the simplest level of comprehension achieved by the reader, where he understands the information and ideas of the text. This level is achieved when the reader understands what the author means in general even if he does not understand what the author wants in specific.
2. ***Reading between the lines***: At this level, the reader shows that he understands what the author specifically wants, and even goes beyond that by extracting meanings and relationships between ideas in the text and even explaining the meanings related to the theme of the text.
3. ***Reading behind the lines***: At this level, the reader uses the information included in the text and applies what he understands in similar situations to get new meanings and ideas.

It is not easy for the learner to acquire reading comprehension. On the contrary, it is a challenge for the teacher and costs him a lot of effort. Several researchers found that the use of mind maps in learning English as a foreign language is a very effective strategy in improving the level of reading comprehension among students (Siriphanich & Laohawiryanan, 2010; Christodoulou, 2010; Liu, Chen & Chang, 2010; Kim & Kim, 2012; Hofland, 2007).

Tony Buzan (2006) established the mind map strategy to enable learners arrange and classify ideas and tasks, and to improve reading, problem solving and decision-making skills. Buzan's mind map was awareness of the educational systems which mainly focus on the left side of the brain. The left side of the brain is responsible for the use of logic, language, arithmetic, sequencing and details of any topic and there was a complete negligence to the right side which is responsible for using colors, images, imagination, emotions and creative (Murley, 2007). Words, images and colors are the primary factor for these maps. Title is placed in center and sub-ideas radiate different branches. This is also called radiant thinking. This concept describes how the brain treats on different ideas and information (Buzan & Buzan, 1996; Siriphanich & Laohawiriyano, 2010; Al-Jarf, 2009). This concept relate to different colors and images that refer to the ideas and using keywords for each concept and all lines are thicker and curvilinear.

Tucker, Armstrong and Massad (2010) found that mind mapping is an important and useful learning strategy as it helps learners to learn and write their notes, organize these notes effectively, and how they can be easily retrieved. Mind map is also an effective tool for slow learners to develop their level of achievement (Holzman, 2004). It also helps to improve our cognitive thinking and long-term memory of facts. Farr and, Hussain and Hennessey (2002) noticed that it encourages deeper level of factual process and better reorganizing the memory.

Earlier researches have proved the impact of the mind map on reading comprehension. Many researchers believed that mind maps have positive effect on reading comprehension. Stankovic, Besic, Papic and Aleksic (2011) found that the mind map was the most powerful tool that used to improve reading comprehension as it enabled the learners to see the relations and links between the main ideas and sub-ideas in addition to the details and notes related to these ideas. Peng (2011) established that mind map increased the level of reading comprehension because it combined the two parts of the brain. It connects among language, words, logical operations and analysis from one side with creativity, Images, construction and imagination from the other. Benavidas, Rivera and Rubio (2010) found that mind map increased the reading comprehension level, increased achievement among the learners and learners change his/her learning style easily and choose an appropriate path for learning.

Siriphanich and Laohawiryanan (2010); Liu, Chen and Chang (2010); Kim and Kim (2012); and Hofland (2007) found that the mind map was an effective strategy in

improving the learners’ reading comprehension skill. The study of Siriphanich and Laohawirynan (2010) also argaed in the same way and opinad that mind maps improved their reading skills. They learn to find out the appropriate relationships between images and drawings. The findings of Gomez’s and King (2014) revealed that images, symbols and links in the mind maps helped the learners to connect between the vocabulary in the texts with these images and symbols. These factors were very helpful for learner to understand the texts and recall the information better.

The problem of this low achievement lies in some aspects: (a) students do not know the meaning of the new vocabulary, (b) students could not summarize the content correctly, and (c) they do not use efficient strategies that help to them understand and comprehend the reading texts. Teachers focus on grammar and neglect the teaching of reading comprehension. This has a negative impact on students’ ability in reading comprehension (Al-Jamal, Al-Hawamleh & Al-Jamal, 2013). Based on the advantages of the mind map and its positive effects on reading comprehension and the different aspects related to this process, this study was conducted by the researcher to explore the impact of the mind map on improving students’ reading comprehension.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. This study aimed at finding out the effect of mind maps on the development of students’ reading comprehension skill in English language.
2. Investigates the students’ attitude towards the use of mind mapping technique.

Framework of the study

In this study the three of main theories were used in teaching procedure as shown in Table 1.

Table1: Three main theories using in teaching procedure

<i>Theories</i>	<i>Teaching procedure</i>
1. Mind mapping	-Teaching vocabularies in pre –reading stage -Represent understanding in reading comprehension in post reading stage
2. Constructivism	-Brain storming to activate vocabularies schema in pre-reading stage - Constructing mind maps and present it to class.
3. Schema theory	-Activate vocabularies’ schema in pre-reading stage.

Table 1. shows that in pre-reading stage, the teacher asked the students to construct mind maps to present their background knowledge about vocabularies related to the reading topic.

In while-reading stage, constructivism theory was used because after reading each section the students had to work in group to answer comprehension questions asked by the teacher.

In post-reading stage mind mapping technique and constructivism theory were used because after answering comprehension questions, the students had to work in groups to construct the mind maps to show the relation of each part of a reading passage

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample

In the present study, the investigator selected 31 students from different colleges under Sidho – Kanho – Birsha university (West Bengal) as sample. The investigator adopted purposive sampling technique for sample selection.

Pre-and Post-Tests

To assess the progress of reading comprehension the pre- and post- test were used. The tests were designed to assess understanding or reading comprehension rather than vocabularies. The test have 30 items with 4 multiple choices. The tests lasted 1 hour.

Data Collection

The experiment was carried out with one class of 1st year students at J. K. College. During the experiment, the students received a total of 24 periods (50 minutes for each) of English language. The teaching process was conducted by the researcher. The overall data collection procedure consisted of the following 1. Administration of the pre-test, 2. Administration of post-test and 3. Questionnaire.

Data analysis

The data analyzed with the SPSS software. Researcher used IBM SPSS statistics v19. Mean scores on the pre-test and post-test were calculated to identify the progress in reading comprehension. T -test was determining significant differences between the mean scores on the pre-and post-test.

FINDINGS

Table 2: Score of reading comprehension before and after using mind mapping technique

Test	N	Mean	S.D.	t	Maximum	Minimum
Pre -test	31	10.17	2.59	2.36*	17	7
Post-test	31	11.25	2.88		21	7

*0.05 level of significance (t=1.69)

By using mind mapping technique, students' English reading comprehension was measured. The pre-test mean score was 10.17, SD was 2.59 while the post-test score was 11.25 and SD was 2.88 which was represented through Table 1. The English reading comprehension post-test mean score of the students was higher than that of the pre-test at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3. The learners' satisfaction on reading comprehension after using mind mapping technique

Questions	Strongly agree percentage	Agree Percentage	Disagree Percentage	Strongly disagree Percentage
The satisfaction of reading ability both in speed and accuracy	11.3	71.4	13.3	0
Enthusiasm for group work activities.	31	45.7	9.4	1.9
The importance of mind mapping in practicing post reading activities.	32.3	57.1	8.6	1
The problems that the students had from writing mind mapping	7.6	39	42.9	7.6
The mind mapping teaching process was clear and helpful for mind mapping writing process.	34.4	60	3.4	0
The application of mind mapping for other subjects.	25.7	52.3	15.1	1

Table 3 proves that the majorities (71.4%) of the students were satisfied with their reading ability both in speed and accuracy, while 60% of them agreed that the mind mapping teaching process was clear and helped them to construct a mind map. Also, slightly more

than half (57.1%) found mind mapping was a useful post reading activity. As for working in groups, almost half (45.7%) agreed that they were enthusiastic to technique in work in groups, and 42.9% had no problems in writing mind mapping.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study shows that after teaching mind mapping techniques, the majority of the students improved their reading ability and their post-test mean score was 11.25 compared to the pre-test mean score which was 10.17. The finding of the study was similar to Alomari (2019) that conducted a study focused on using mind mapping techniques to improve the reading comprehension ability of fourth-grade Arabic language students in Jordan. Furthermore, utilization of mind mapping techniques in teaching and learning aids, students in thinking skills, establishing relationships, analyzing, focusing and showing creativity. Siriphanic and Laohawiriyano (2010) who found that the mind-map involves students to think and communicate information to become a simple one. It also leads students to conduct semantic mapping and helps students to activate their prior knowledge before doing reading activities (Zahedi & Abdi, 2012).

Khatimah and Rachman (2018) state the mind mapping technique can improve students' reading and writing skills because before reading students are asked to do writing exercises. The results of this study are in agreement with those seen from previous researches which demonstrated that mind mapping technique can enhance the students' reading ability. (Maestas & Croll, 1985; Deesri, 2002; Singtui, 2008). Trevino (2005), Al-Jarf, (2009) and Hourani (2011) discussed the use of mental maps as an educational technique in many school subjects and found that the use of these maps created positive attitudes towards learning these subjects, especially the use of electronic mental maps is simple. They also added that working on these maps in the computer lab created a competitive atmosphere among students, who showed their skills in making these mind maps. Designing these maps, showing the ideas in the given texts indicated a better understanding of these texts. The study findings were consistent with the results of the Moi and Lian (2007) who proved that students were able to retrieve answers effectively from the mental map, understand reading texts better and recall information and thus understand texts better and faster.

Despite the fact that the teaching process was considered helpful, it can be improved. Time and the amount of practice, for instance, can be spent more effectively. During pre-reading stage, the teacher should take more time to teach both vocabularies and provide them with activities that they can draw on their prior knowledge to activate the schema. As for extracting main ideas and summarizing stories, the teacher can encourage the students by providing them with shorter reading passages to practice. To solve such a problem, the teacher should assign a specific role for each of them rather than leaving them in groups and doing the task without any clear guidance.

REFERENCES

- Al-Jamal, D., Al-Hawamleh, M., & Al-Jamal, G., (2013). An Assessment of Reading Comprehension Practice in Jordan. *Jordan Journal of Educational Sciences*, 9(3), 335-344.
- Al-Jarf, R. (2009). Enhancing Freshman Students' Writing Skills with a Mind Mapping software. Paper presented at the 5th International Scientific Conference, *eLearning and Software for Education* (9-10 April 2009). Bucharest.
- Alomari, Akram M. (2019). Using mind mapping technique to improve reading comprehension ability of fourth-grade Arabic language students in Jordan. *IOSR Journal of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 24(1), 53-58.
- Al-Tal, S. (1992). Athar El Surah Al Qiraiya Wa Mustawa El Maqroiya Wal Jins fi Elisteaab ElQirai' Li Talbat El Saf El Thamin. *Abhath El Yarmuk, Silsilat Al Ulum El Insania*, 8(4), 9-44.
- Benavides, S., Rivera, F., & Rubio, M., (2010). Improving reading comprehension skills by using mind -mapping software with students of bachelor's degree in English attending reading and writing in English II course. (Master thesis) Universidad de Oriente UNIVO. San Miguel, El Salvador.
- Burns P., & Roe. B. (2002). *Informal rea ding inventory*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Buzan, T. (2006). *Mind Maps for Kids: An Introduction*. Harper Thorsons, Hammersmith, London.
- Buzan, T., & Buzan, B. (1996). *The mind mapping bo ok: How to use Radiant Thinking to maximize your brain's untapped potential*. London: BBC.
- Christodoulou, K. (2010). *Collaborative on-line concept mapping*. (Master's thesis). University of Manchester. UK
- Durkin, A., & Dolores. (1995). *Teaching them to Read*. New York: Allyn Bacon Company.
- Farrand, S., Hussain, F. & Hennessy, E. (2002). The efficacy of the mind map study technique. *Journal of Medical Educational*, 36(5), 426-431.

- Gómez, M., & King, G. (2014). Using mind mapping as a method to help ESL/EFL students connect vocabulary and concepts in different contexts. *TRILOGÍA. Ciencia, Tecnología y Sociedad*, 10, 69-85.
- Grellet, F. (1995). *Developing reading skills: A practical guide to reading comprehension exercises*. London: CUP.
- Hofland, C. (2007). *Mind-mapping in the EFL classroom*. Fontys Hogescholen: Fontys Teacher Training College Sittard.
- Holzman, S. (2004). *Thinking maps: Strategy-based learning for English language learner*. Annual Administrator Conference 13th Closing the Achievement Gap for Education Learner Student, Sonoma County Office of Education, California Department of Education.
- Hourani, H. (2011). *Athar Istikhdam Al-Khara'et Al-Thihniyyah fi Tahseel Talabat Al-saff Al-tase' fi maddat Al-Uloum wa fi Etijahatihim nahwa al-uloum fi Al-madares Al-hokoumiyyah fi Madinat Qalqeelyah, Nablus*. Al-Najah National University.
- Khatimah, K. & Rachman, D. (2018). Mind mapping vs semantic mapping: Which technique gives EFL learners more benefits in reading comprehension?. *JEES (Journal of English Educators Society)*, 3 (2), 165-176.
- Kim, S. Y., & Kim, M. R. (2012). Kolb's Learning Styles and Educational Outcome: Using Digital Mind Map as a Study Tool in Elementary English Class. *International Journal for Educational Media and Technology*, 6(1), 4-13.
- Kim, S. Y., & Kim, M. R. (2012). Kolb's Learning Styles and Educational Outcome: Using Digital Mind Map as a Study Tool in Elementary English Class. *International Journal for Educational Media and Technology*, 6(1), 4-13.
- Lakshmi, L., & Rao, D. (2006). *Reading and Comprehension*. New Delhi: Discovery Publishing House.
- Lipson, M., & Wixson, K. (2009). *Assessment and instruction of reading and writing difficulties, an interactive approach (4th Edition)* Pearson Boston.
- Liu, P. L., Chen, C. J., & Chang, Y. J. (2010). Effects of a computer -assisted concept mapping learning strategy on EFL college students' English Reading Comprehension. *Computers & Education*, 54(2), 436-445.

- Moi, W., & Lian, O. (2007). *Introducing Mind Map in Comprehension*. Educational Research Association, Singapore. Retrieved October 7, 2017, from <http://conference.nie.edu.sg/2007/paper/papers/LAN469.pdf>
- Ortlieb, E. (2013). Using Anticipatory Reading Guides to Improve Elementary Students' Comprehension. *International Journal of Instruction*, 6(2), 145-162.
- Peng, S. (2011). The effect of combining mind map and electronic picture-books on fourth-graders' reading comprehension ability and reading motivation. (Master's thesis). Taiwan: National Pingtung University of Education.
- Siriphanich, P., & Laohawiriyano, C. (2010). Using mind mapping technique to improve reading comprehension ability of Thai EFL university students. In the 2nd International Conference on Humanities and Social Sciences (pp. 1–13).
- Smith, C. B. (1997). Vocabulary instruction and reading comprehension. *ERIC Digest*, ED 412506.
- Stankovic, N., Besic, C., Papic, M., & Aleksic, V. (2011). The evaluation of using mind maps in teaching. *Technics Technologies Education Management*, 6(2), 337-343.
- Trevino, C. (2005). Mind-mapping and outlining: Comparing two types of graphic organizers for learning seventh-grade life science. (Unpublished Ph.D. thesis). USA: Texas Tech University.
- Tucker, J. M., Armstrong, G. R., & Massad, V. J. (2010). Profiling the mind map user: A descriptive appraisal. *Journal of Instructional Pedagogies*, 2(4), 1-13.
- Zahedi, Y., & Abdi, M. (2012). The semantic mapping strategy on EFL learners' vocabulary learning. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 69, 2273–2280.